

Energy Demand Modelling for Developing Economies Using MAED-2 with Sectoral Decomposition: Bangladesh Case Study

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Abstract

Access to affordable, clean energy and its growing consumption have often been directly linked with socio-economic development. As one of the fastest developing countries, Bangladesh has been experiencing stable GDP growth with an increasing trend for the last ten years. This growth has initiated excessive demand for energy, especially in the electricity sector. Within just a decade, both the total electricity generation capacity and per capita electricity generation have almost doubled. In order to meet this growing demand and keep pace with the development trend, sectoral demand growth projection for near and long-term planning and execution is essential. Model for Analysis of Energy Demand (MAED)-2 tool provided by International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) was used in this study to predict the future energy demand in Bangladesh from the year 2020 to 2050. The energy-economic data of the year 2015 is considered as the base data. Future energy demands based on different socio-economic and demographic development scenarios have been projected and decomposed into sectoral demands that identifies the transition of a traditional agriculture-based society in to an industry-service oriented society. The insights obtained from analysis could be further utilized in policy development for energy security and climate change actions so that the development would be sustainable.

Keywords : Energy Demand, Electricity, Bangladesh, MAED model

1. Introduction

Energy is widely regarded as one of the key elements of social well-being and sustainable development. The demand and consumption of energy grows as the human society transforms from hunting-gathering and agricultural to industrial and information-based entities. Especially for developing economies, the growth in the energy sector is rapid due to the transformations in socio-economic and techno-industrial arenas. In order to keep up with the growing energy demand, policy level intervention is essential considering energy security and climate change issues. That is why demand forecasting is one of the most important components of energy system modelling.

Bangladesh, listed as one of the Least Developed Countries by the United Nations (UN), is also one of the fastest developing nations currently. Over the last decade, the country has observed steady economic growth, which in turn has been followed by high energy demand growth, particularly in the electricity sector as more people get access to clean and reliable form of energy. More than 165 million people live in a small land area of 147,570 square kilometers and their hunger of energy is growing over time. Traditionally, indigenous natural gas accounts for the major share of primary energy supply in Bangladesh, almost 60% of the total primary energy demand¹⁾. Due to over dependency on single

resource and slow growth in discovery of new gas reserves, Bangladesh might face severe shortage of natural gas in near future which poses the threat of losing energy self-dependency and becoming an obstacle in the way of development. In order to identify and explore alternative options, proper energy demand forecasting is very important considering current socio-economic growth patterns. Several studies are available done by researchers and the government mainly focusing on individual sectors²⁾ or energy sources such as natural gas³⁾ and electricity⁴⁾. However, analysis relating the economic sectors with overall final energy demand that projects the complete picture is still not available.

Modelling energy systems for developing countries is a challenging task as many of the existing models are biased towards the industrialized countries ignoring the informal economy, supply shortages, poor performance of the power sector, structural economic change, electrification, traditional bio-fuels, urban-rural divide⁵⁾ and above all transition of the socio-economic dynamics during the analysis period. S. C. Bhattacharyya et al.⁶⁾ compared some of the widely used energy demand forecasting models from developing countries perspectives and concluded that only MAED⁷⁾ and LEAP have the generic capabilities to be used in a wider context specifically applicable for the developing countries. The most prominent feature of the MAED-2 model is its flexibility for representing structure of energy consumption and disaggregate it according to

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the needs and/or data availability as developing countries often do not have sufficient historical data.

MAED model has been previously widely used to analyze the energy demand scenario for developing economies including Syria ⁸⁾ and Tanzania ⁹⁾. In this study, we customize the generic MAED-2 model based on historical data and energy-economic demand disaggregation to project the future final energy demand of Bangladesh. In the consecutive sections, we describe the generic MAED methodology along with the customizations made, calibrate the model with historical data, obtain results for different socio-economic and demographic scenarios and finally explain the insights obtained from the analysis which could be useful in policy level decision making.

2. Methodology

MAED model forecasts future energy demand based on medium- to long-term scenarios of socio-economic, technological and demographic developments. The model relates systematically the specific energy demand for producing various goods and services identified in the model, to the corresponding social, economic and technological factors that affect this demand. Energy demand is disaggregated into a large number of end-use categories e.g., cooking, lighting, air cooling, steel production, pumping water for farmland, passenger transportation by train; each one corresponding to a given service or to the production of a certain good. The total energy demand for each end-use category is aggregated into four main “energy consumer” sectors: Industry (including Agriculture, Construction, Mining and Manufacturing), Transportation, Service and Household. The nature and level of the demand for goods and services are a function of several determining factors, including population growth, number of inhabitants per dwelling, number of electrical appliances in the households, peoples’ mobility and preferences for transportation modes, national priorities for the development of certain industries or economic sectors, the evolution of the efficiency of certain types of equipment, market penetration of new technologies or energy forms etc. The expected future trends for these determining factors, which constitute scenarios, are exogenously introduced.

The MAED model software has two modules: MAED_D and MAED_EL. The MAED_D processes information describing the social, economic and technological scenario of development and calculates the total energy demand for the desired years. The breakdown of this demand by energy form and by economic sector considered is also provided as part of the results of the analysis. The MAED_EL module uses the total annual demand

for electricity in each sector (calculated in MAED_D) to determine the total electric power demand for each hour of the year or, in other words, the hourly electric load, which is imposed on the power system under consideration. In this analysis, we limit within the MAED_D module, as our primary focus is the overall energy demand rather than the electricity sector in particular.

Fig. 1 Scheme to project final energy demand in MAED_D

MAED_D generic equation [9], in which energy demand in future year is determined, could be simplified as in equation 1.

$$ED_t = \frac{ED_b}{DP_b} \times CH_t \times DP_t \quad (1)$$

Where, ED_t represents energy demand in future analysis year, t (ED_b / DP_b) - Specific energy demand per unit of driving parameter (e.g. population, GDP growth) in base year, b

CH_t - Coefficient to reflect evolution of specific energy demand due to socio-techno-economic changes per unit of driving parameter in future year, t

DP_t - Driving parameter creating energy demand in future year, t .

Fig. 1 shows the general structure of MAED_D modelling procedure comprising the following sequential calculation steps:

- Breakdown of the structure of final energy into various consumption sectors of end-use by fuel type and energy form;
- Identification of social, economic and technological driving factors influencing each category of final consumption and their relations to the final energy;
- Reconstruction of the final energy consumption based on the statistical data available for the base year of the study (the financial year 2015 was used for this study);
- Construction of consistent development scenarios with respect to the evolution of demographic, macroeconomic, socio-economic and technological factors influencing the energy demand;
- Evaluation of final energy demand, including electricity corresponding to each scenario during the study period.

3. Model Development

3.1 Sectoral Decomposition

In order to evaluate sectoral contribution and composition of energy usage, four main consumption sectors including Industry, Transportation, Household and Service were considered. The industry includes four sub-sectors that comprise agriculture, construction, mining and manufacturing. The transportation sector was subdivided into passenger and freight transport, both by air, road, rail and water modes. The household sector is subdivided into urban and rural parts with energy demand arising from cooking, lighting, air-conditioning and usage of electrical appliances. The service sector mainly considers thermal, electrical and motive power consumption from different demands.

3.2 Model Calibration

The starting point for using the MAED_D model is construction of base year energy consumption patterns within the model. This requires compiling and reconciling necessary data from different sources, deriving and calculating various input parameters and adjusting them to establish a base year energy balance. This helps to calibrate the model to the specific situation of the country. In order to develop the energy consumption patterns for the base year 2015, historical data from 1990 to 2015 at 5 years interval has been used. The base year energy balance obtained from model calibration was observed to be in close match with the historical data.

3.3 Scenario Development

Different scenarios were developed for sensitivity analysis of the

model at different demographic and socio-economic situations. Medium, low and high variant (95% prediction interval) population projections proposed by the United Nations ¹⁰⁾ were considered for the analysis as shown in **Fig. 2**. Population distribution in the country (e.g. urban and rural), population mobility growth, which also influence the energy demand, were considered unchanged for the different scenarios.

Fig. 2 Population projection for Bangladesh

Three different socio-economic scenarios in terms of GDP growth rate has also been considered named as Business As Usual (BAU), Low Growth (LG) and high growth (HG). These scenarios consider the currently increasing GDP growth rate reaches 8% by the year 2020 and from that point linearly decrease up to 4%, 5% and 6% for the LG, BAU and HG scenarios respectively. The GDP growth projections for the scenarios are in coherence with the projections made by ADB ¹¹⁾, IMF ¹²⁾ and PricewaterhouseCoopers ¹³⁾.

3.4 Economic Transition

Bangladesh is one of the developing regions that is going through a transformation in the economy from agriculture dependent to more industry oriented. Several ongoing mega infrastructure projects have created huge demand of steel, cement and technology based services. Per-capita steel consumption almost doubled from 24 kg in 2010 to 45 kg in 2017 in Bangladesh ¹⁴⁾ and it is supposed to grow in coming years. The current growth trends in the industry, service and agriculture sectors have been analyzed to project future contribution to the economy ¹⁵⁾ and those results have been adopted in this analysis for better representation of the economic shift.

3.5 Technological Evolution

Technological evolution and energy efficiency improvements play a significant role in determining future demand growth. As the GDP per capita improves, more rural people get access to clean energy for cooking rather than traditional biomass. Moreover, access to air conditioning systems and usage of electrical appliances increases. However, efficiency improvements play a key role to resist energy demand growth mostly in the household and service sectors which have been taken into consideration during the model calibration. Industry sector however, is more energy sensitive. Energy intensity in the industry sector is supposed to decrease as energy efficiency improvement initiatives take place over the years. The historical trend up to 2015¹⁶⁾ and future projection of energy intensity, that has been used as input of this model is presented in Fig. 3. The dynamic interplay among various driving forces from various end-users determine the overall system dynamics which have been taken into consideration during the model calibration and future projection.

Fig. 3 Energy intensity trend and projections for Bangladesh

3.6 Transportation Sector

The energy demand of the transportation sector is calculated directly in terms of final energy as a function of the total demand for transportation of passengers (passenger-kilometers) and freight (ton-kilometers), the breakdown of this demand by competing modes (car, bus, plane, truck, train etc.) and the specific energy needs and load factors of each mode. For transport of passengers, the distinction is made for urban (intracity) and intercity transport. The total demand for transport is calculated separately for freight and passengers according to macro-economic and life-style factors. In the case of freight transportation, the demand is calculated as a function of the GDP contribution (t-km/monetary unit) from the economic subsectors. On the other hand, the demand for transport of passengers is determined from total population, percentage of population living in large cities, and the average intercity and intracity distance traveled per person, which were considered fixed in the analysis.

4. Results Analysis

The computation was carried out under three different socio-economic growth scenarios- BAU, LG and HG. The BAU case was further analyzed for three different population projections namely medium, low and high variant. Per-capita final energy demand for different scenarios are presented in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4 Per-capita final energy demand for different scenarios

At the same economic growth (BAU-case) and different population scenarios (low, medium and high variant), per capita final energy demand increases in ascending order from high, medium and low variant population projections. In order to maintain the growth of development and upgrade in the human development index, per capita energy consumption plays an important role. Historical per capita energy consumption and projected per capita energy demand support this fact and paves the pathway for Bangladesh to reach up to the level of developed countries. Bangladesh is likely to be the biggest mover in the global GDP ranking (from 42nd to 26th position) by the year 2030¹⁷⁾ and even may achieve the 23rd position by projected GDP ranking at PPPs¹³⁾ as one of the fastest growing countries¹⁷⁾.

Fig. 5 Per-capita energy consumption of different countries in 2017 and the projection for Bangladesh in 2050

As energy consumption is directly linked with economic development, we can compare the projected per-capita consumption for the country in 2050 (BAU Growth and medium

variant population) with some other countries of the world with latest data of 2017¹⁸⁾ as shown in **Fig. 5**. The comparison depicts that Bangladesh may not reach the level of highly industrialized and developed regions like Japan or European Union by 2050. However, it has the potential to become one of the emerging economies with growing industries and higher primary energy consumption like Brazil, Indonesia and India.

If we compare the five different scenario results as presented in **Fig. 6**, at the same medium variant population projection, 1% GDP growth increase (from Low growth to BAU and BAU to High growth) induces around 14% increase in the per capita energy demand in the year 2050. Whereas, considering same economic growth level (BAU), 1% increase in population (from Low variant to medium and medium variant to high) results in around 0.5% decrease in per capita energy demand for the same year of 2050. Therefore, economic growth plays more significant role than population change with respect to per capita energy demand. The BAU growth with medium variant population is decomposed in **Fig. 6**. The sectoral dynamics with contribution from different sectors confirm that industry sector would start dominating the energy sector as well as the economy with highest growth. Growth in the household sector is relatively low due to efficiency improvement in cooking, air conditioning and electrical appliances even though the total consumption doubles from 2015 to 2050. Transport and service sectors also face steady growth as economic activities increase significantly and technological evolutions continue at the same time.

Fig. 6 Sectoral energy demand growth for BAU economic growth with medium variant population

As electricity is one of the major sources of secondary energy and its contribution directly effects people’s quality of life, it gets special attention in the analysis. The electricity sector might

experience continuous growth due to increase in rural electrification growth, incorporation of current off-grid solar projects into the national grid and successful implementation of the national grid strengthening projects including interconnection with neighboring countries. The electricity demand projection for the three different socio-economic growth scenarios have been further investigated using the MAED_EL model considering seasonal variations and impact of economic shift. The MAED_EL model development for the Bangladesh electricity sector and projected electricity demand at hourly resolution from different economic sectors have been discussed in¹⁵⁾.

Analyzing the transportation energy demand for 2050 as shown in **Table 1**, it is evident that economic growth and industrialization induces mobility mostly for freight due to increased economic activities. However, at same economic level, passenger transportation demand varies proportionally with respect population whereas freight demand remains stable. Even though both passenger and freight transportation energy demands are dependent on economy and population, the basic model formulation of MAED_D and the structure of the current software restricts the flexibility to consider both the factors simultaneously.

Table 1 Transportation Energy Demand in 2050

Scenarios	Freight Demand (Mtoe)	Passenger Demand (Mtoe)
Low Growth Medium Population	7.25	3.14
BAU Growth Low Population	8.56	2.95
BAU Growth Medium Population	8.56	3.14
BAU Growth Low Population	8.56	3.33
High Growth Medium Population	10.09	3.14

5. Conclusion

Energy demand modelling for developing countries is different from already developed and industrialized countries as both the economy and population change faster. Economic transition from agriculture to industry and services have bigger impact on the energy demand sector growth. In this study, we analyzed the impact of different socio-economic growth scenarios along with population variations to observe the impact on final energy demand. During the process of model development and calibration, historical data was utilized to customize the generic MAED_D model for the specific country and time horizon. The current analysis for Bangladesh identifies the main focus sectors with potential high growth and it also signifies the contribution of secondary energy like electricity to meet up the demand arising specially from the industry sector.

Developing countries often face several obstacles during the process of transition from a low-income country to middle-income country due to lack of insights for policy making. Countries like Bangladesh often get misguided by prescribed policy plans prepared from inappropriate models from donor agencies with ulterior motives. In this analysis, we customized a widely used energy demand model, customized and calibrated it according to available historical data and obtained useful information from the results. These results could be further utilized to investigate individual sectors in detail. We plan to continue the current research with special focus on the electricity sector and apply MAED_EL to get details of the bottom-up engineering sectors. Energy demand model for other developing nations could also be analyzed for different scenarios following this case study for Bangladesh using the MAED_D model.

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